

Evaluation of Salivary Nickel Level During Orthodontic Treatment

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Abstract : Since nickel is a known toxic and carcinogenic metal, the present study was designed to evaluate the level of nickel released into the saliva of orthodontic patients. Non-stimulated saliva was collected from 18 patients attending The Orthodontic Clinic of Dental Faculty of Benghazi University. Patients were divided into two groups and level of nickel was determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometry. Nickel concentration values (mg/L) in first group prior to starting treatment was 0.097 ± 0.071 . An increase in level of nickel was followed by decrease 4 and 8 weeks after applying the arch wire (0.208 ± 0.112) and (0.077 ± 0.056 mg/L) respectively. Nickel levels in saliva of the second group were showed minimal variation and ranged from 0.061 ± 0.044 mg/L to 0.083 ± 0.054 throughout period of study. It may be concluded that there could be a release of nickel from the appliance used in first group but it doesn't reach toxic level in saliva.

Keywords : atomic absorption spectrophotometry, nickel, orthodontic treatment, saliva, toxicity

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